

Improving the Quality of Clustered texts based on Distance Metrics

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Abstract

Manual analysis of this unstructured textual data is impractical, and as a result, numerous text mining methods are being developed to automate the process of analyzing this unstructured data. The stringent distance metrics technique used in the paper to increases the accuracy of the clusters formed with lesser execution time and lesser memory usage. This work has provided an overview of clustering and the factors to check and measure the quality of clustered texts. This work has showcased two distance measure namely Hamming and Levenshtein to edit and modify the misspelled strings present in the extracted files and also reduction factor metric is measured to improve the quality of clusters.

Keywords: *Clustering, Distance Metrics, Cluster Quality ,Filtering Techniques*

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1. Introduction

Computations are performed based on these factors to arrive at a score that determines how well a person would fit into the Google “culture”. The filtering programs vary significantly, the simpler filters may provide very basic assistance to a company’s human resource department whereas the more complex ones may employ sophisticated techniques such as those used by Google. Irrespective of which mechanism is applied, the trend of using filters is growing tremendously. Employers across the globe states that using resume filtering technique eliminates around 70 to 85% of the unpromising resume documents. However, applying strict filters to a set might adversely affect the search (Norm Scheinder *et al.*, 2011). Enforcing exceptional search criteria may result in certain prospective candidates’ resumes being ignored. Even though strict filters might accuracy with which the results are computed are so impressive that the recruiters and hiring managers have started to favor electronic methods for determining suitable candidates (Abhishek Sainani, 2011[1]). The advent of internet has facilitated colossal numbers of resumes received on-line, through emails and through references. Most of the firms find it difficult and time consuming process to select the appropriate resume from such huge volume of resumes. Plethora of research work related to extract appropriate resumes from the abundant volume of resume data are being carried out to improve the performance of resume selection process. Usually, resumes consist of document-level hierarchical contextual structure where the correlated data units occur in different categorized textual block. The primary problem is to reduce the large volume of resumes to a few hundred potentially related resumes used to speed up the recruitment process based on hi-tech filtering techniques or extraction techniques.

The extracted number of resumes is similar to each other as they fulfill the requirement criteria or requirements for a company. Presently the resume has to be manually analyzed to select appropriate resumes. The problem of selecting resumes is defined as “Problem of resume selection from huge set of resumes. The primary goal of the research is to develop an improved approach which could help in selecting appropriate resume by processing resume datasets.. A recent survey found that about 78% of the employers were content with investing in the online recruiting domain (Dolan, 2002 [3]). The resumes in the online format are scanned and processed using information extraction methods, which are then stored in the employer’s resume repository (Xing Yi *et al.*, 2007 [8]). When a recruiter requires some resumes, he/she performs a keyword search on this resume database. This search uses dynamic filtering techniques. The set of filters help in tossing out irrelevant resumes. Google uses “resume filters” to sift through the piles of resumes it gets every month for every job posted. Online job applicants provide some personal information that helps the recruiter to delve into factors such as attitude, behavior, and personality traits.

2. Stringent techniques used in the Clusters:

2.1. Number of Clusters

The final result produced will be in the form of clusters and the number of clusters formed by the algorithm shows the effective working of the approach used in the algorithm. The cluster formation varies a lot since the distance metrics used in the algorithm produces different number of clusters for the same set of resume dataset. The most important feature of the algorithm is it produces less number of clusters but the clusters are relevant and accurate to cater to the need of the employers. The stringent feature extraction and conversion technique used in the algorithm increases the accuracy of the clusters formed with lesser execution time and lesser memory usage.

2.2. Speed of Execution

The most important parameter which defines the excellent performance of an algorithm is the execution time, if the algorithm consumes lesser time to produce results, then the algorithm is said to be an efficient one. One of the main objectives of this work is to reduce the running time and ensure speed in the execution and fulfilled this objective in style. The problem related to the execution time is a major hitch for every researcher and a separate section in this work deals with this running time. This section provides a clear insight about the main objective of this work (i.e.) discovering relevant resumes from the large datasets with minimum running time.

2.3. Memory Convention

The memory consumption in text mining is one of the major things which have to be addressed with utmost care and should be avoided. (Dixon *et al.*, 2001[2]) explained that larger datasets with large number of tokens, the texts will not fit in memory and the algorithm will trash due to exceedingly higher memory occupation. Since the memory utilization is directly proportional to the number of text extracted, we have to implement a tradeoff technique to make sure that the text extracted as well as the memory utilization is low when compared with the existing algorithms.

3. Improving Cluster Quality Using Distance Metrics:

Text mining is one of the many techniques used to extract meaningful information from the documents. Document clustering is defined as unsupervised document feature extraction and automatic fast information extraction from huge set of documents. Recently it is being extensively used for browsing documents and fetches information from the documents. Clustering is defined as combining a set of physical or abstract objects into classes of similar objects. In that case, every set of objects clustered are similar to one another within the cluster and dissimilar from other clusters (Fahrni *et al.*, 2012[4]). Major requirement of clustering in data mining includes scalability, proficiency to deal with diverse attributes, adeptness to deal with noisy and large data,

interoperability and usability. Clustering can be defined as the process of generating similar groups of objects. Each cluster generated is a collection of objects which are similar in some method or way. Clustering normally deals with finding a similarity in an unstructured collection of unlabeled data. The approach in this use strict clustering technique to group the resumes which are similar to exactly one cluster alone. The main difficulty here, while clustering arises from the technical text where the spelling of the technical keyword may differ and this problem is solved by using hamming distance. The lookup table for the technical keywords is being employed to find the hamming distance of the technical keyword and here the specific skill is the most important object to select and recruit the prospective candidates from the resume dataset.

The hamming distance between two strings of equal length is calculated by generating a sequence of Boolean values indicating the match and mismatch between the corresponding positions of the characters in the input strings (Kun Yu *et al.*, 2005[5]). The hamming distance H is defined only for the strings of same lengths and let us assume S_1 and S_2 be the two strings, $H(S_1, S_2)$ is the number of places in which the two strings S_1 and S_2 differs. The Levenshtein distance is calculated to make sure the prospective resumes are not left behind without clustering because of the misspelled words present in the resumes and this modification of misspelled words improves the clustering quality to a greater extent. The main intention of the proposed approach is based on the study that for each job requisite, the employer needs to be offered with best possible resume matches with the important data they look for. The extracted resumes should highlight critical data such that it takes only a second to decide the next level prospective candidates. The Levenshtein distance edits the cluster objects and improves the quality of clustering to a greater extent. The usage of this edit distance never ignores the prospective candidates during the selection process and the precision of the extracted resume steeply increases. The cleaned, filtered, converted and extracted texts from the resume dataset are clustered according to various parameters enabling the employer to discover the exact matches of candidates he/she needs. This work has provided an overview of clustering and the factors to check and measure the quality of clustered texts This work has showcased two distance measure namely Hamming and Levenshtein to edit and modify the misspelled strings present in the extracted files.

4. Cluster Quality improved based on weightage:

. The weightages are calculated and the highest weightages are clustered together and makes the life easier for the employer to filter and extract the prospective resumes from the huge resume datasets. The table 1 displays the resultant clusters formed with the common features along with the experience. The weightages are important here as the clusters are formed according to the weightage and category values formed during the feature extraction and category conversion . (Jayaraj *et al.*, (2015) [7]) stated that weight ages and categorical conversion enhances the clustering speed and memory usage considerably. Let us assume to find resumes for a job requirement of a Java Developer with 5 years of experience with minimum Master's degree as education criteria. The

resume dataset contains thousand resumes for enhance the quality. Graphical presentation for Clustered results is noted in Figure 1. Hence the accuracy of resumes discovered by the algorithm is higher order.

Figure 1. Graphical presentation for Clustered results.

Common Cluster Feature	Resume ID	Experience
Java Programmer	R13, R14, R19 , R22, R28, R29, R33, R34, R39, R48, R52, R76, R80, R83, R92, R9, R119, R138, R139, R141, R167, R169, R198, R297, R299, R320, R323, R327, R378, R381, R406	JA3
	R11, R45, R49, R117, R179, R194, R315, R405, R412, R416, R421, R422, R485	JA5
Python Developer	R37, R86, R90, R116, R134, R155, R184, R193, R202, R222, R271, R361, R362, R375, R453, R482, R494	PH2
Oracle Developer	R60, R61, R73, R88, R118, R138, R139, R141, R155, R162, R178, R249, R271, R273, R285, R308, R309, R333, R351, R389, R400, R407, R414, R453, R461, R462, R465, R466, R473, R475, R479, R484	OR4
	R44, R63, R67, R125, R158, R187, R206, R233, R251, R272, R304, R417, R490	OR4

Table 1: Clustered Results for Programmer - Java, Oracle, Python

5. Performance Metrics

The performance metric to check the clustering quality is defined as reduction factor (RF) that measures the reduction in the number of resumes under consideration. (Guhasudipto *et al.*, 2001[9]) .Let ‘N’ be the total number of resumes present in the resume dataset that match the criteria using filtering technique and template employed and ‘M’ denote the number of resumes acquired after executing the final process algorithm.

$$\text{Reduction factor RF}_{(\text{job requirement})} = 1 - (M / N) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$\text{Reduction factor RF}_{(\text{Age})} = 1 - (\sum_{c=1}^n A(c)) / A \text{ -----(2)}$$

$$\text{Reduction factor RF}_{(\text{Skills})} = 1 - (\sum_{c=1}^n S(c)) / S \text{ -----(3)}$$

Based on this factors, Reduction factors are evaluated for 500 numbers of sample resumes and its performs well. The evaluated values for the job requirement, Age, Skills regarding reduction factor is shown. This process considers only the job specification or category like “java developer”, “Dot net Programmer” for calculations. The reduction factors are found and to ease the filtering of the resumes, weight ages corresponding to the parameters are taken and reduction process is carried out. To find the specific skill reduction factor, the calculated productivity weight age values plays a major role during clustering, higher the productivity weight age, more are the chances for the resumes to form a cluster.

Figure 2: Reduction factor calculated

The figure shows the reduction factor values calculated for three parameters namely for job requirement, Age and Skillsets. The reduction factor values for age is low mainly because of the categorization of the age done during the feature extraction and conversion. From the figure it is observed that the reduction factor is low for some skills and medium for some skills since some of the skills are common in most of the resumes.

This new approach delivers better results and reduction factor as compared to many of the existing approaches as the employer discovers relevant resumes matching the most significant requirement criteria highlighting the specific skill features present in the resumes. Let us assume to find resumes for a job requirement of a Java Developer with 5 years of experience and with skills related to J2ME, JSP, Stub with minimum Master's degree as education criteria. The existing approaches would fetch all the resumes with the "Java" keyword as the skill category or job requirement. But this approach fetches the resumes with "Java Developer" as their general skillset along with the educational criteria (master's degree) filtered according to the educational weight age and the specific skills required by the recruiters with the productivity weight age score. Hence the accuracy of resumes discovered by this approach is high and the precision and recall values of this approach will be of higher order when compared with the existing approaches.

6. Conclusion:

This work has provided an overview of clustering and the factors to check and measure the quality of clustered texts . This work has showcased two distance measure namely Hamming and Levenshtein to edit and modify the misspelled strings present in the extracted files. The quality of the clustered is identified based on the reduction factor performance distance metric with good accuracy. Finally, the ultimate goal of this research work is to make the computer read various resumes like human beings and discover satisfactory results by identifying the prospective candidates resume at high without any manual process.

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